

ENHANCING LEARNING WITH INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

Makhliyobonu Makhmadovna Azizova,

Teacher, Department of Uzbek and Foreign Languages
Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport

ABSTRACT

This scientific article is helped to engage you, the reader, in a process of looking at the promises, pitfalls and new practicalities associated with information and communication technology—looking at them through a lens which is framed in terms of principles of effective learning.

Keywords: education technology, evaluate and embed, ‘learning technologists’, the natural process of learning, The Apple Classrooms of Tomorrow (ACOT).

АННОТАЦИЯ

Эта научная статья призвана вовлечь вас, читателя, в процесс рассмотрения перспектив, подводных камней и новых практических аспектов, связанных с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями, через призму принципов эффективного обучения.

Ключевые слова: образовательные технологии, оценка и внедрение, «технологи обучения», естественный процесс обучения, Apple «Классы завтрашнего дня» (КЗО)

INTRODUCTION

As I sit pondering the threads I wish to weave in this paper I am struck by the paucity of this medium—one composed of text and line graphics—to convey the fullness of what I want to communicate! Those of you who know me, or who have heard me speak, will no doubt add other dimensions—you may hear my voice, inject my personal tone and even heave a sigh of relief that you have control over the pace with which you process what I am saying. For those of you who don’t know me, my communication with you is totally dependent on my skill in using verbal language to convey meaning in a linear string. My ‘knowing’ of what I wish to communicate, however, is not linear. It is multi-layered and multi-modal—visual, emotional, anecdotal, factual, propositional, conceptual—and it does not translate easily to a

verbal linear thread. This morning I received my first html email message that contained photographic images and sound. As I listened and looked with amazement, I marvelled at the powers of new information and communication technologies that enable almost instantaneous communication, across the boundaries of time and space, in multi-modal form. My mind reels at what these new technologies make accessible at the click of a few buttons, not to mention some frustrating time delays. I ponder on the new and different demands—new practicalities— that these new information technologies place on educators. Then I turn my attention to the nature of my ongoing work on understanding what stimulates, supports and enhances learning and I am struck by the fact that many educators are still not skilled users of learning technology let alone information technology.

Methodology. Learning technology and information technology.

If we think of technology as ‘the applied science of . . .’, then information technology is application of the science of information and information systems and results in the development of tools for managing information. Learning technology, on the other hand, is the applied science of learning. It is the application of all that we know about human learning to develop strategies and tools for enhancing and managing learning. Following this line of thought, education technology includes learning technology and information technology. Technologies for education will include a focus on the ‘soft systems’ (mind processes and collaborative processes), the ‘hard systems’ (computers) and the interactions and interfaces between the different systems—Figure 1, below.

The capacity of tools of information technology—computers and electronic storage of data; computer networks and the internet; software programs ranging from word processing to spreadsheets to multi-media—to process, transfer and store information moves the emphasis away from the teacher as being the holder of the information and frees the teacher to act more as a learning technologist. In a world rich in information technology, the authority of the teacher no longer lies in being the one who knows. Rather it is in being the one who knows about knowing and learning and in being the one who has deep understanding of aspects of the powerful ideas and processes captured in collective human wisdom.

What of learning in formal learning settings?

For some learners learning in a formal setting mirrors what happens for them in informal learning settings - these learners are in the minority. For other learners, learning with some teachers mirrors learning in informal settings. However, for most

learners, learning in formal settings rarely mirrors learning in informal settings. For most students learning in formal settings involves the filling up of the world we 'know about', but don't 'know'; the world other people 'know about' but we do not know— Figure 5. These learners know about World War II but don't know its connection to their own experience of conflict; they know about levers and machines but don't connect it to their own experience of lifting loaded wheelbarrows; they know about Pythagoras' theorem but don't know how to use it to square a building. They know what they need to know to regurgitate on exams.

Figure 5 Formal learning as learning to 'know about' and know about what others 'know'

Making it happen

The Apple Classrooms of Tomorrow(ACOT) project is an excellent resource for learning about what is possible when classrooms become information technology rich. Their recent publication, *Teaching with technology: Creating Student-centred Classrooms* (Haymore Sandholtz et al, 1997), documents the experiences of ten years of learning in classrooms richly endowed with information technology. One very clear outcome of the ACOT project is that information technology has facilitated the development of student-centred classrooms and the trend in ACOT schools is for there to be a shift from 'instruction to construction'—Table 1. Of course you can have learning situations that are based on a learnercentred, constructivist approach that do not use information technology which is any more modern than a book. Similarly, you can have learning situations which have access to all the latest information technology but are very teacher-centred and focus almost solely on 'drill and kill'. So what enables or disables the shift? What are the practicalities?

	Instruction	Construction
Classroom activity	Teacher centered Didactic	Learner centered Interactive
Teacher Role	Fact teller Always expert	Collaborator Sometimes expert
Student role	Listener Always learner	Collaborator Sometimes expert
Instructional emphasis	Facts Memorization	Relationships Inquiry and invention
Concept of knowledge	Accumulation of facts	Transformation of facts
Demonstration of success	Quantity	Quality of understanding
Assessment	Norm referenced Multiple-choice items	Criterion referenced Portfolios and performances
Technology use	Drill and practice	Communication, collaboration, information access, expression

Table 1 Contrasting views of instruction and construction *Source: Haymore Sandholtz, 1997:14*

Consider again, Promise 1: Information technology relieves teachers of the burden of being the information source and redefines their role as ‘learning technologists’.

Practicalities: Students often know more about information technology than teachers. Whether teachers like it or not, students are often the ‘expert’ while teachers are the learners. And even if the students are not experts, the teachers are generally learners when it comes to information technology. With the rapid rate of change in available information technology it is hard not to be continually a learner. Somehow information technology ‘gives permission’ for the roles to change. It is okay not to know.

Although teachers generally have a rich experiential knowledge about learning those who have articulated it clearly are in the minority. If teachers are going to be supported in becoming learning technologists, inservice courses, pre-service courses and teacher conversations will need to continue to focus on:

- deepening understanding of learning
- the development of learning strategies
- the development of collaborative, student-centred learning
- developing approaches for learning to learn.

The ACOT research indicates that the role shift is likely to be evolutionary rather than revolutionary. Those of you who made a shift from being strongly teacher-centred to student-centred will no doubt identify with this.

Information rich but learning poor?

Information technology has provided easy access to information and information in multiples modes. Virtual reality even has the capacity to stimulate senses other than our sense of hearing and sight. But an information rich environment

is no guarantee of learning. Although human understanding can be embedded in software (for example accounting packages which guide the accounting ignoramus through processes to complete accounting procedures) humans cannot simply gain understanding by direct transfer from a computer any more that they could gain understanding from direct transfer of notes from the board. Human understanding requires processing in the individual's mind. You can transfer information but understanding has to be developed. Processing for understanding cannot be left to chance.

How can we ensure that information rich is not learning poor?

As we integrate information technologies into our practice, classrooms will only become information rich and learning rich if we attend to all the features which enhance learning in any learning situation. Information technology may have changed things in that it makes more possible, however those possibilities will only result in enhanced learning if we attend to the application and refinement of powerful learning technologies. On that front the scene has not changed.

Questions used to stimulate metacognition
<i>What do you know and what do you want to know?</i>
<i>What's the 'big idea'?</i>
<i>What are some of the little ideas?</i>
<i>What can you do now that you could not do before?</i>
<i>How did you learn that?</i>
<i>Compare how you learned it with how others learned it?</i>
<i>What do you understand now that you did not understand before?</i>
<i>What do you want to know now?</i>
<i>What will it look like, feel like and sound like when you have finished?</i>
<i>What questions do you have?</i>

Table 3 Questions used to stimulate a metacognitive approach

Information technology and the 'world of possibilities'

One of the fascinating things about the knowledge era is the transformation of what we have considered to be normal in the late industrial era. For example, in the industrial era if I gave away my key assets I no longer had them; if I gave away my property I no longer had it. In the knowledge era, if I give away my key asset, knowledge, I still have it. What is more, it is likely to have grown in the process of giving it away. Not only has my knowledge been maintained or grown, but the collective knowledge in the particular community of learners has grown. As indicated earlier in the paper, in the knowledge era traditional hierarchies such as teacher-learner, publisher-writer are being dismantled. Much is made possible in terms of empowering individual learners in an unstratified world of learners.

CONCLUSION

The possibilities are endless—we will be limited only by the limits of our imagination and by hanging-on to outdated mind sets. One of the powerful features of mental models is that they give us a sense of order in chaos; a degree of predictability

and comfort. They can, however, be our greatest enemy straight-jacketing us in concepts suitable for a different time. In the words of the ancient Hebrew proverb: Do not confine your children to your own learning, for they were born in a different time.

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